

Towards new elements involved in the transport of magnesium and cobalt in *Salmonella* serovar Typhimurium: The “Cor” proteins

Our recent publication has shed light on the importance of magnesium in the ability of quiescent *Salmonella* cells to resume growth (Metaane *et al.* 2022).

Salmonella imports magnesium *via* three known transporters, the widely conserved CorA transporter and the MgtA and MgtB P-type ATPases (Papp-Wallace *et al.* 2008) (Fig.1). CorA is expressed under various growth conditions whereas the other two magnesium transporters, MgtA and MgtB, are expressed under conditions of magnesium starvation under the positive control of the PhoP-PhoQ regulatory system (Groisman *et al.* 2021). CorA can perform magnesium influx and efflux and it is also able to import cobalt and nickel when these elements are present in high concentrations in the growth medium (Papp-Wallace *et al.* 2008, Groisman *et al.* 2021 and 2013, Maguire 2006, Moomaw and Maguire 2008). Thus a $\Delta corA$ mutant is more resistant to cobalt (*cor* stands for “cobalt resistant”) and nickel than the wild-type strain. Our recent finding that *corA* is activated by the stress sigma factor sigmaS/RpoS in stationary phase *Salmonella* (Metaane *et al.* 2022, Metaane *et al.* 2023) prompted us to assess the physiological impact of a $\Delta corA$ mutation on quiescent *Salmonella* cells by analytical and global analyses (Metaane *et al.* 2023).

Figure 1- Magnesium trafficking in *S. Typhimurium*.

OM outer membrane, PG peptidoglycan, IM inner membrane, C cytoplasm

CorA proteins are a unique class of transporters and are widespread in the Bacteria and Archaea, with functional homologs in eukaryotes. Many questions about CorA and its full role in *Salmonella* physiology remain unanswered (Metaane *et al.* 2023). During the study of magnesium

and cobalt transport by CorA in *Salmonella*, three loci named *corB*, *corC* and *corD*, involved in resistance to cobalt and magnesium efflux have been discovered (Gibson *et al.* 1991) (Fig.1). The *cor* mutants selected carried spontaneous mutation or transposon insertion and displayed a level of cobalt resistance that was intermediate between that of the wild-type strain and that of the $\Delta corA$ mutant. This study proposed that CorB, CorC and CorD contribute to the efflux of divalent cations by CorA, either by coupling the transport of cations by CorA to an energy source, or as a cation sensor for the CorA protein (Gibson *et al.* 1991). Efflux by CorA requires high extracellular magnesium concentrations (10 mM in minimal medium (Snavely *et al.* 1989), therefore probably more in LB rich medium). Under magnesium deficiency conditions, magnesium efflux is undetectable in *Salmonella* (Snavely *et al.* 1989). The *corB*, *corC* and *corD* genes have not been further characterized in *Salmonella* and their function remains unclear to date. We have identified the *corB*, *corC* and *corD* genes as corresponding to the *yffD*, *ybeX* and possibly *apaG* genes, respectively, in *Salmonella* serovar Typhimurium strain ATCC14028. We have constructed deletions in these genes in order to study their physiological impact in *Salmonella*.

The CorD/ApaG protein

The bacterial CorD/ApaG protein consists of a single conserved domain named ApaG or DUF525 which is also found within the F-boxes of eukaryotic proteins (CNNF family). This F-box domain is described as a motif that mediates protein-protein interactions (Kipreos and Pagano 2000). As CorD/ApaG (as well as all Cor proteins) is suspected to have a role in magnesium homeostasis (Gibson *et al.* 1991), possible interactions between the ApaG domain of the human protein FBxo3 and divalent ions was evaluated. NMR and spectrometry experiments showed that the ApaG domain of FBxo3 does not interact with Mg^{2+} nor with Co^{2+} (Krzysiak *et al.* 2016). In prokaryotes, *apaG* belongs to the *pdxA-ksgA-apaG-apaH* operon which is involved in the metabolism of dinucleotide phosphates (Blanchin-Roland *et al.* 1986) (Fig.2). The ApaH protein is a hydrolase responsible for the degradation of dinucleotides phosphates which accumulate during metabolic stress. the PdxA polypeptide is required for pyridoxine synthesis and the KsgA enzyme is a methyltransferase that modifies the 16S unit of ribosomal RNA in *E. coli* (Roa *et al.* 1989). No interaction between the ApaG domain of FBxo3 and diadenine phosphates was observed (Krzysiak *et al.* 2016). The ApaG protein comprises a core composed of seven beta sheets surrounded by four loops (Fig.3).

Figure 2 - Genetic environment of the *apaG* gene of *S. Typhimurium* ATCC14028.

Annotations are specified for genes surrounding *apaG*

<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/kegg2.html>

Figure 3 – Protein structure of the ApaG protein from *Xanthomonas citri* obtained by crystallography. PDB ID: 2F1E

The CorB/YfjD protein

Recently, the CorB protein of *S. Typhimurium* was identified as belonging to the CNNM family (Funato and Miki 2019) (Fig.4). The family of “cystathionine- β -synthase (CBS) domain magnesium transport mediators”, “Cyclins M” or CNNMs is a family of ubiquitous proteins involved in the transport of divalent metal cations. The CNNMs family is mainly studied in eukaryotes because four proteins (CNNM1-4) are present in humans (Giménez-Mascarell *et al.* 2019). This family was created quite recently (first occurrence on Pubmed in 2012) and all of its members have probably not yet been identified. In bacteria, the best-known member of the CNNM family is the MgtE protein. CNNMs are membrane proteins which comprise at least one transmembrane domain (DUF21 domain of unknown function) and a large cytosolic region composed of two CBS domains (cystathionine- β -synthase) (Giménez-Mascarell *et al.* 2019). “CBS pair” domains are small intracellular modules that pair to form a stable globular domain. Pairs of these domains have been called the Bateman domain and are found in many proteins, such as AMP-activated protein kinases, or the CorC protein for example (Baykov *et al.* 2011). Eukaryotic CNNM proteins also possess the DUF21 domain and the CBS pair, but differ from prokaryotic CNNMs in having a large extracellular N-terminal domain and an intracellular cyclic nucleotide-binding (CNBH) domain (Cheng *et al.* 2018). In addition, prokaryotic CNNMs have a different C-terminal domain, the CorC or CorC-HlyC domain (Chen *et al.* 2021). The CorC or CorC-HlyC domain can be found in some Na⁺/H⁺ antiporters and in proteins of the TerC family involved in resistance to some cations (Paruthiyil *et al.* 2020). Crystallography of truncated forms of the CNNM2 protein revealed that the “CBS-pair” of the CNNMs dimerize (Fig.4) (Gómez-García *et al.* 2012). In doing so, they form disk-like structures that enclose central nucleotide binding sites for Mg²⁺-ATP (Corral-Rodríguez *et al.* 2014). CBS domains, by binding to ligands such as ATP, could play a regulatory role by making proteins sensitive to adenosyl-bearing ligands. Although CNNM proteins are associated with magnesium transport, it remains unclear whether these proteins are magnesium transporters or regulate other magnesium transporters. Recently, the structure of a CNNM protein from *Thermus parvatiensis* was described (Huang *et al.* 2021ab). Note that this laboratory calls this protein CorC while it is the CorB protein, as stipulated by the authors of a second article describing the structure of CorB from *Methanoculleus thermophilus* (Chen *et al.* 2021). The CorB binding sites for magnesium (Huang *et al.* 2021a) and ATP (Chen *et al.* 2021, Huang *et al.* 2021b) have been identified and a model has been proposed in which CorB mediates Mg export (Fig.5). In *Staphylococcus aureus*, the CorB protein has been named MpfA for Magnesium Protection Factor A (Armitano *et al.* 2016). Indeed, the $\Delta mpfA$ mutant is unable to grow in the presence of 40 mM MgCl₂ unlike the wild-type strain. Similarly, the $\Delta mpfA$ mutant is more resistant to CoCl₂ 1 mM than the wild-type strain (Armitano *et al.* 2016). Considering that cobalt toxicity is probably due to competition

between Co^{2+} and native ions to bind to cytoplasmic enzymes, it was hypothesized that Mg^{2+} toxicity could act similarly and that MpfA allows the efflux of magnesium. The ΔmpfA mutant would be less sensitive to cobalt toxicity due to an intracellular concentration of Mg^{2+} high enough to compete with Co^{2+} (Armitano *et al.* 2016). In *S. Typhimurium*, the *yjfD/corB* gene is preceded by *corE* which might be involved in the maturation of cytochrome C (Thöny-Meyer *et al.* 1995) (Fig.6). Despite its name, CorE has not been shown to be involved in cobalt sensitivity.

Figure 4 – Structure and organization of CNNM/CorB carrier domains.

(a) Phylogenetic tree of representative orthologues of the CNNM/CorB family generated by the “neighbour joining” method. (b) Domain organization of eukaryotic CNNM proteins and prokaryotic CorB protein. TMD corresponds to the transmembrane domain, AHB to the acidic helices, CNBH is a cyclic nucleotide-binding homology domain and CorC corresponds to the CorC-HlyC domain (c) Structure obtained by crystallography of the CorB protein of *Methanoculleus thermophilus* (CorBMT). (d) Topology of a CorBMT protein monomer comprising: in blue, the transmembrane and juxtamembrane helices, in yellow, the acidic helices, in green, the Mg^{2+} -binding CBS domain and in gray the CorC domain. Figure adapted from Chen *et al.* (2021).

Figure 5 – Proposed model for CorBMT from *Methanoculleus thermophilus*. In the absence of Mg^{2+} -ATP binding, the CBS domains (in green) and the transmembrane domain (in blue) are in contact, which inactivates the transmembrane domain. When Mg^{2+} -ATP is bound, contact between the CBS domains and the transmembrane domain is weakened, allowing the transmembrane domain to transport Mg^{2+} . The domain represented in yellow corresponds to the acidic helices (AHB domain). Figure adapted from Chen *et al.* (2021).

STM14_3281 *ffh* signal recognition particle protein
 STM14_3282 putative cytochrome c-type biogenesis protein (heme exporter)
 STM14_3283 *corE* hypothetical protein
 STM14_3284 *yjfD*
 STM14_3285 putative cytoplasmic protein
 STM14_3286 *grpE* heat shock protein GrpE/ molecular chaperone GrpE
 STM14_3287
 STM14_3288 *ppnK* inorganic polyphosphate/ATP-NAD kinase
 STM14_3289 *recN* recombination and repair protein/ DNA repair protein RecN (Recombination protein N)

Figure 6 - Genetic environment of the *yjfD* gene of *S. Typhimurium* ATCC14028.

Annotations are specified for genes surrounding *yjfD*

<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/kegg2.html>

The CorC/YbeX protein

In some reports, the CorC/YbeX protein is considered as a member of the extended prokaryotic CNNM family. This protein is composed of the “CBS pair” domain and a CorC-HlyC domain found in proteins of the prokaryotic CNNM family. On the other hand, the membrane DUF21 domain present in the members of the CNNM family is not found in CorC. CorC domains thus correspond to the cytoplasmic domains of prokaryotic CNNM proteins such as CorB. CorC/YbeX is therefore probably a cytoplasmic protein. The structure of the YbeX protein of *E. coli* has been resolved by crystallography (PDB ID: 4HG0, Fig.7). In *Francisella tularensis*, the *ybeX* mutation causes an increase in cytokine levels in macrophages (Russo *et al.* 2011). An interaction between YbeX and GdcA, a glycosyltransferase which affects the stimulation of immune cells in *Francisella tularensis*, has been demonstrated (Nau *et al.* 2019). The GdcA protein does not seem to be conserved in *Salmonella* and *E. coli* (KEGG database). In *Salmonella*, it has been reported that the biological function of CorC requires the presence of the CorA protein (Gibson *et al.* 1991). However, it should be noted that some bacterial species such as *Francisella*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* and *Legionella pneumophila*, have homologs of CorC but not of CorA (Nau *et al.* 2019). Therefore, it is possible that YbeX plays a broader role than that proposed in magnesium homeostasis. In *E. coli*, the *ybeX* gene has been identified, *via* a transcriptomic study, as a member of the σ^{32} regulon (Nonaka *et al.* 2006). In *S. Typhimurium*, the *lnt* gene which codes for an essential N-acyltransferase protein, involved in the synthesis of lipoproteins is located downstream of *ybeX* (Fig.8) (Cheng *et al.* 2018). It cannot be excluded that *lnt* is, at least in part, co-transcribed with the *ybeX* gene. The *ybeX* gene is surrounded by other genes coding for important functions in the cell, such as maturation of ribosomal RNAs (Fig.8).

Figure 7 – Structure of the YbeX protein of *E. coli* K12 obtained by crystallography. PDB ID: 4HG0. The protein was found as a dimer.

STM14_0773 **gltI** glutamate and aspartate transporter subunit
 STM14_0774 hypothetical protein
 STM14_0775 **Int** apolipoprotein N-acyltransferase
STM14_0776 ybeX/corC
 STM14_0777 conserved hypothetical protein
 STM14_0778 **ybeY** putative metalloprotease/ probable rRNA maturation factor
 STM14_0779 **phoL** putative phosphate starvation-inducible protein
 STM14_0780 hypothetical protein
 STM14_0781 **miaB** rRNA modification protein

Figure 8 - Genetic environment of the ybeX gene of *S. Typhimurium* ATCC14028
 Annotations are specified for genes surrounding *yjfD* <https://www.genome.jp/kegg/kegg2.html>

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RESULTS

We have constructed deletions in the *corB/yjfD corC/ybeX* and *corD/apaG* genes in order to study their physiological impact in *Salmonella*.

Sensitivity of the $\Delta corC$, $\Delta yjfD$ and $\Delta apaG$ mutants to cobalt and nickel toxicity was evaluated by using the disk method (Experiment M13). On LB plates, the $\Delta corA$ strain was the only mutant more resistant to the cations than the wild-type strain. On M63 minimal medium containing 1 mM MgSO₄, the $\Delta corA$ mutant was fully resistant, whereas the $\Delta corC$ and $\Delta yjfD$ mutants displayed a level of resistance which was intermediate between that of the wild-type strain and that of the $\Delta corA$ mutant. On M63 starved for magnesium, the $\Delta corA$ and $\Delta corC$ mutants were very resistant whereas the $\Delta yjfD$ strain showed a level of resistance intermediate between that of the $\Delta corA$ mutant and that of the wild-type strain. The sensitivity of the $\Delta apaG$ mutant was similar to that of the wild-type strain whatever the medium.

In conclusion, our data validated the resistance phenotype of the $\Delta corC$ and $\Delta yjfD$ mutants to cobalt and nickel toxicity on minimal medium, even if their resistance level was lower than that of the $\Delta corA$ mutant. On the other hand, no significant effect of the $\Delta apaG$ mutation could be observed.

We then determined whether combination of mutations could increase the resistance level of *Salmonella* to cobalt and nickel toxicity (Experiment M14). On LB plates, all the mutants carrying the $\Delta corA$ mutation were resistant to cobalt. On M63 plates with Mg 25 μ M or 1mM, the level of resistance afforded by the mutations was : $\Delta corA > \Delta corC > \Delta yjfD > WT = \Delta apaG$. In addition, strains were more sensitive to cobalt and nickel on M63 starved for Mg (25 μ M) than on M63 containing Mg 1 mM. In summary, the data confirmed our previous conclusions and further showed that the effects of mutations are not cumulative.

The absence of effect of the $\Delta apaG$ mutation was surprising. Because *apaG* is probably the first gene of an operon (*apaG apaH*), we constructed and assessed the phenotype of the $\Delta apaH$ mutant (Experiment M15). Interestingly, in contrast to the $\Delta apaG$ mutant, the $\Delta apaH$ mutant was more resistant to cobalt and nickel than the wild-type strain on M63 plates. This finding suggests that ApaH instead of the ApaG is involved in cobalt sensitivity.

Since the *cor* loci were suspected to play a role in magnesium efflux *via* CorA, we also determined the sensitivity of the wild-type and mutant strains to magnesium toxicity. It was not possible to evaluate magnesium toxicity using the disk method because *Salmonella* is very resistant to magnesium. Magnesium toxicity was therefore assayed in liquid medium. Since CorA has been reported to be required for magnesium efflux in *Salmonella*, we first compared the sensitivity of the wild-type and $\Delta corA$ strains using magnesium doses between 0 and 150 mM (Experiment M2 and M3). Growth of the $\Delta corA$ strain was clearly affected when LB was supplemented with 50, 100 or 150 mM MgCl₂ (Experiment M2). When bacterial growth was followed not only by the OD₆₀₀ of the culture but also by viable cells measurement, an extended lag phase of the $\Delta corA$ strain was clearly observed (Experiment M3). We therefore used these conditions to assess potential magnesium sensitivity afforded by the other *cor* mutations, alone and in combination (Experiments M9 and M10).

In conclusion, our study validated the impact of YbeX and YjfD in cobalt and nickel sensitivity and revealed that ApaH, but not ApaG, plays a role in cobalt and nickel sensitivity. Concerning magnesium toxicity, in the conditions used, the $\Delta corA$ mutant was the only mutant affected

when growth was evaluated in LB containing magnesium 150 mM. The growth of strains carrying $\Delta ybeX$, ΔyjD and $\Delta apaG$ mutations, alone or in combination, was not affected under these conditions. The growth of the $\Delta apaH$ mutant was slightly affected but to a lesser extent than that of the $\Delta corA$ mutation.

We have further characterized the $\Delta ybeX$ mutant of *Salmonella*. Our data revealed a physiological role of *ybeX* when *Salmonella* is grown under conditions of magnesium starvation (Kumar *et al.*, manuscript in preparation).

EXPERIMENT M13 : Cobalt and nickel toxicity (see M13-images)

Diameters of growth inhibition around the disk (CoCl₂ or NiCl₂)

Strain	40 µl CoCl ₂ 0.1 M	40 µl NiCl ₂ 0.5 M	Bacterial suspension 5 10 ⁶ B/ml on agar plates	Genotype
6910	19	24	LB	WT
G564	15	22	LB	$\Delta corA \Delta km$
F787	19	24	LB	$\Delta corC::km$
H923	19	24	LB	$\Delta corC\text{-Int } \Delta km$
H539	19	24	LB	$\Delta yjjD \Delta km$
H540	19	24	LB	$\Delta apaG \Delta km$
6910	25	44	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	WT
G564	9	25	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta corA \Delta km$
F787	17	37	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta corC::km$
H923	17	37	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta corC\text{-Int } \Delta km$
H539	18	40	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta yjjD \Delta km$
H540	25	44	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta apaG \Delta km$
6910	17	37	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	WT
G564	9	20	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta corA \Delta km$
F787	10	27	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta corC::km$
H923	12	28	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta corC\text{-Int } \Delta km$
H539	13	34	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta yjjD \Delta km$
H540	17	37	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta apaG \Delta km$

EXPERIMENT M14 : Cobalt and nickel toxicity (see M14-images)

Diameters of growth inhibition around the disk (CoCl₂ or NiCl₂)

Strain	40 µl CoCl ₂ 0.1 M	40 µl NiCl ₂ 0.5 M	Bacterial suspension 5 10 ⁶ B/ml on agar plates	Genotype
6910	21	24	LB	WT
F787	21	24	LB	Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
G564	14	22	LB	Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm
H341	15	23	LB	Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
H539	20	24	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm
H540	20	25	LB	Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm
H709	19	24	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
H710	19	24	LB	Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
H772	19	26	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm
H778	19	25	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
H811	14	23	LB	Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm
H840	15	22	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm
H852	15	22	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
H923	20	24	LB	Δ <i>corC</i> -IntΔkm
I34	14	23	LB	Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> -IntΔkm
I178	15	22	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> -IntΔkm
I179	19	23	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> -Int::km
I180	19	24	LB	Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> - Int::km
I181	19	24	LB	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> -Int::km
I183	15	22	LB	Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> -Int::km

Strain	40 µl CoCl ₂ 0.1 M	40 µl NiCl ₂ 0.5 M	Bacterial suspension 5 10 ⁶ B/ml on agar plates	Genotype
6910	25	44	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	WT
F787	18	38	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
G564	9=R	27	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm
H341	9=R	28	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>corA</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
H539	21	42	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm
H540	25	44	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm
H709	18	37	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
H710	19	38	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km
H772	19	41	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm
H778	18	38	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	Δ <i>yfjD</i> Δkm Δ <i>apaG</i> Δkm Δ <i>corC</i> ::km

H811	9=R	26	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔcorAΔkm ΔyjfDΔkm</i>
H840	9=R	25	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorAΔkm</i>
H852	10≈R	26	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorAΔkm ΔcorC::km</i>
H923	17	35	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔcorC-IntΔkm</i>
I34	10≈R	27	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔcorAΔkm ΔcorC-IntΔkm</i>
I178	10≈R	26	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorAΔkm ΔcorC-IntΔkm</i>
I179	17	35	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔyjfD Δkm ΔcorC-Int::km</i>
I180	17	35	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorC-Int::km</i>
I181	17	35	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorC-Int::km</i>
I183	10≈R	26	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	<i>ΔcorAΔkm ΔyjfDΔkm ΔcorC-Int::km</i>

Strain	40 µl CoCl ₂ 0.1 M	40 µl NiCl ₂ 0.5 M	Bacterial suspension 5 10 ⁶ B/ml on agar plates	Genotype
6910	19	39	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	WT
F787	13	29	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔcorC::km</i>
G564	10≈R	24	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔcorAΔkm</i>
H341	9=R	23	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔcorAΔkm ΔcorC::km</i>
H539	14	34	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm</i>
H540	19	40	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔapaGΔkm</i>
H709	13	28	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔcorC::km</i>
H710	13	29	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorC::km</i>
H772	13	34	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm</i>
H778	13	28	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorC::km</i>
H811	9=R	22	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔcorAΔkm ΔyjfDΔkm</i>
H840	9=R	22	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorAΔkm</i>
H852	10≈R	22	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorAΔkm ΔcorC::km</i>
H923	12	28	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔcorC-IntΔkm</i>
I34	9=R	24	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔcorAΔkm ΔcorC-IntΔkm</i>
I178	10≈R	20	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorAΔkm ΔcorC-IntΔkm</i>
I179	12	27	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfD Δkm ΔcorC-Int::km</i>
I180	12	26	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorC-Int::km</i>
I181	13	27	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔyjfDΔkm ΔapaGΔkm ΔcorC-Int::km</i>
I183	9=R	21	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	<i>ΔcorAΔkm ΔyjfDΔkm ΔcorC-Int::km</i>

EXPERIMENT M15 : Cobalt and nickel toxicity (see M15-images)

Diameters of growth inhibition around the disk (CoCl₂ or NiCl₂)

Strain	40 µl CoCl ₂ 0.1 M	40 µl NiCl ₂ 0.5 M	Bacterial suspension 5 10 ⁶ B/ml on agar plates	Genotype
6910	20	25	LB	WT
G564	15	22	LB	$\Delta corA\Delta km$
H539	20	25	LB	$\Delta yjjD$
H540	19	24	LB	$\Delta apaG$
H541	19	24	LB	$\Delta apaH$
H923	20	24	LB	$\Delta corC\text{-Int}\Delta km$
6910	18	39	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	WT
G564	9	20	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta corA\Delta km$
H539	13	34	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta yjjD$
H540	19	39	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta apaG$
H541	11	25	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta apaH$
H923	11	28	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 1 mM)	$\Delta corC\text{-Int}\Delta km$
6910	26	45	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	WT
G564	9	26	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta corA\Delta km$
H539	21	42	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta yjjD$
H540	26	45	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta apaG$
H541	17	36	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta apaH$
H923	18	37	M63 glucose 20 mM (Mg 25 µM)	$\Delta corC\text{-Int}\Delta km$

EXPERIMENT M2 : Magnesium toxicity

Bacterial growth in LB supplemented or not with MgCl₂

EXPERIMENT M3 : Magnesium toxicity

Bacterial growth in LB supplemented or not with MgCl₂

EXPERIMENT M9 : Magnesium toxicity

Bacterial growth in LB supplemented or not with MgCl₂

EXPERIMENT M10 : Magnesium toxicity

Bacterial growth in LB supplemented or not with MgCl₂

- WT (6910)
- $\Delta apaH$ (H541)
- $\Delta apaH \Delta yfjD \Delta corC$ (I221)
- $\Delta corA$ (G564)
- $\Delta corA \Delta apaH \Delta yfjD \Delta corC$ (I219)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Construction of mutants

Chromosomal deletions were generated in *Salmonella* ATCC14028 using PCR-generated linear DNA fragments and λ -Red recombination-based method (see references in Metaane *et al.* 2022, 2023). All strains were confirmed to contain the expected mutation by DNA sequencing.

Bacterial strains used : All strains are derivatives of *Salmonella* Typhimurium ATCC14028

Strain	Characteristics	Source or reference
VF6910	ATCC14028 <i>Salmonella enterica</i> serovar Typhimurium, wild-type strain	American Type Culture Collection
VFG564	ATCC14028 $\Delta corA\Delta Km$	Metaane <i>et al.</i> 2023
VFF787	ATCC14028 $\Delta corC::Km$	This study
VFH915	ATCC14028 $\Delta corC-Int::Km$	This study
VFH923	VFH915 with the Km cassette eliminated	This study
VFH378	ATCC14028 $\Delta yfjD::Km$	This study
VFH539	VFH378 with the Cm cassette eliminated	This study
VFH394	ATCC14028 $\Delta apaG::Km$	This study
VFH540	VFH394 with the Cm cassette eliminated	This study
VFH396	ATCC14028 $\Delta apaH::Km$	This study
VFH541	VFH396 with the Cm cassette eliminated	This study
VFI203	H541 $\Delta yfjD::Km$	This study
VFI216	VFI203 with the Km cassette eliminated	This study
VFH762	VFH539 $\Delta apaG::Km$	This study
VFH772	VFH762 with the Km cassette eliminated	This study
VFH709	VFH539 $\Delta corC::Km$	This study
VFI179	VFH539 $\Delta corC-Int::Km$	This study
VFH722	VFG564 $\Delta yfjD::Km$	This study
VFH811	VFH722 with the Km cassette eliminated	This study
VFH779	VFH772 $\Delta corA::Km$	This study
VFH840	VFH779 with the Km cassette eliminated	This study
VFH778	VFH772 $\Delta corC::Km$	This study
VFI181	VFH772 $\Delta corC-Int::Km$	This study
VFH710	VFH540 $\Delta corC::Km$	This study
VFI180	VFH540 $\Delta corC-Int::Km$	This study
VFI183	VFH811 $\Delta corC-Int::Km$	This study
VFH341	VFG564 $\Delta corC::Km$	This study
VFI11	VFG564 $\Delta corC-Int::Km$	This study
VFI34	VFI11 with the Km cassette eliminated	This study
VFI221	VFI216 $\Delta corC-Int::Km$	This study
VFH852	VFH840 $\Delta corC::Km$	This study
VFI178	VFH840 $\Delta corC-Int::Km$	This study

Oligonucleotides used for construction of mutants

Name	Sequence (5' – 3')	Construction
yfjD-P1	TCCGAAACTGGAATGATGACGCTAAACC GTTACCGTTTACGCGTGT AGGCTGGAGCTGCTTC	$\Delta yfjD::Km$
yfjD-P2	CCGGAGTTCGCCATTGTGTTACTCCGCCACACTCTCGCGCAGCATA TGAATATCCTCCTTAG	$\Delta yfjD::Km$
apaG-P1	CTTTGAAGGAGAGTTAAACATGATCAATTCGCCCAGAGTGTGTGTG TAGGCTGGAGCTGCTTC	$\Delta apaG::Km$
apaG-P2	TGCCATTGTTATAATTTTAGTGAATGAGTGTAGGACGGCGGAGCAT ATGAATATCCTCCTTAG	$\Delta apaG::Km$
apaH-P1	ATTCATAAAAATTATAACAATGGCAACTTATCTCATCGGCGACGTG TAGGCTGGAGCTGCTTC	$\Delta apaH::Km$
apaH-P2	GCGCCATCAGGCATAAACCTATCAGGCGTTGACCGCTTCGCCATA TGAATATCCTCCTTAG	$\Delta apaH::Km$

STM14-0776-P1	CTAACATGAGAACCCATACGACGCCATGAGCGACGACAATTCAGT GTAGGCTGGAGCTGCTTC	$\Delta corC::Km$
STM14-0776-P2	GGCAAATGCCATTTTATGTCCTACTATTGCTGTATTTCGTCAGCATA TGAATATCCTCCTTAG	$\Delta corC::Km$
STM14-0776-P1	CTAACATGAGAACCCATACGACGCCATGAGCGACGACAATTCAGT GTAGGCTGGAGCTGCTTC	$\Delta corCInt::Km$
ybeX-P2Int	GCAGCAGGCGAATACGCTGGCGTTCAATTAACGAGGCAAATGCCA TATGAATATCCTCCTTAG	$\Delta corCInt::Km$

Cobalt and nickel sensitivity

A bacterial suspension containing 5×10^6 CFU/ml was prepared in saline buffer from stationary phase bacteria grown in LB rich medium for 18h at 37°C. This suspension was spread on agar LB and on agar M63 minimum medium containing MgSO₄ 25 μM or 1 mM and plates were left to dry for 30 minutes. A 9 mm disc (Whatmann) placed in the center of the plate was soaked with 40 μl of 0.1 M CoCl₂ or of 0.5 M NiCl₂. Plates were incubated overnight at 37°C and the growth inhibition diameters around the disc were measured.

Magnesium sensitivity

Salmonella strains were grown to stationary phase in LB at 37°C and diluted into fresh LB supplemented with different concentration of MgCl₂. Growth was followed by measuring the optical density of the culture (OD₆₀₀) and viable cells (CFU/ml).